

LINGUISTIC ASPECTS OF THE TRANSLATION OF MEMOIR WORKS

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Abstract

A memoir is a non-fiction story written from the author's point of view, recounting and reflecting on a particular event or series of events in his or her life. These events are usually important turning points in the author's life, leading to some kind of personal discovery that changed the direction of his life or his view of the world. Essentially, memoirs are excerpts from the author's own life that are retold with the intention of making the memoir as true and factual as possible. In this article, the linguistic and cultural aspects of the translation of memoirs are considered on the example of James David Vance's "A Memoir of a Family and Culture in Crisis".

Key words. Memoir, author, life story, non-fiction story, memories, linguistic and cultural aspects.

Аннотация

Мемуары — это научно-популярный рассказ, написанный с точки зрения автора, рассказывающий и размышляющий о конкретном событии или серии событий в его или ее жизни. Эти события обычно являются важными поворотными моментами в жизни автора, ведущими к какому-то личному открытию, изменившему направление его жизни или его взгляд на мир. По сути, мемуары представляют собой отрывки из собственной жизни автора, которые пересказываются с целью сделать мемуары как можно более правдивыми и основанными на фактах. В данной статье лингвокультурологические аспекты перевода мемуаров рассматриваются на примере книги Джеймса Дэвида Вэнса «Мемуары о семье и культуре в условиях кризиса».

Ключевые слова. Мемуары, автор, жизнеописание, научно-популярный рассказ, воспоминания, лингвокультурологические аспекты.

INTRODUCTION

Just because a memoir isn't fiction doesn't mean it's not considered a "literary" form of writing. Memoirists often zoom in on specific events in their "real life" and describe those events in detail using creative storytelling techniques. This means that

memoirs need the same building blocks that any story needs—scene, characters, drama, dialogue, and plot. The style and language used in writing a memoir are as important as the subject matter. It's not just what you say, but how you say it. The skill of a good memoirist is to use narrative techniques to make everyday, real things new, interesting, and strange.

This is an excerpt from *A Memoir of a Family and Culture in Crisis*, one of the many memoirs in James David Vance's collection, and "when was the last time you saw your father?". Notice how James weaves in vivid images to describe the traffic scene to make it more interesting and unique.

His neck seems stiff; his head is bent a little forward from the shell of the tortoise: it seems as if it had been pushed behind to overcome the recession in front, the literal disappearance of the face. After sipping from a clear plastic cup of water, his hands tremble slightly. He seems to be standing on the other side of some invisible partition, a screen of pain.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Memoirs are often confused with autobiographies because they are self-written biographies. However, the difference is simple. Autobiographies provide a complete chronological account of someone's life from birth to death. It involves more of a factual record of one's life, as opposed to studying one's memories. Memoirs, on the other hand, magnify particular events that are memorable only to the author. They capture these moving memories with great attention to detail and deal with the author's thoughts as much as they do in the actual moment.

Although the content of memoirs is unique in that it is personal and specific to its authors, all memoirs tend to contain certain recurring characteristics.

The author of this memoir, James David Vance, wrote about the Appalachian values of his Kentucky family and the social and socioeconomic problems of his hometown of Middletown, Ohio, where his mother's parents moved when they were young.

Vance talks about his upbringing and family while growing up in Middleton, Ohio. She writes about a family history of poverty and low-paying, manual jobs that later disappeared or became less secure, and contrasts this with her perspective on life after she left.

Although Vance grew up in Middletown, his mother and her family were from Breathitt County, Kentucky. Their Appalachian values include traits such as loyalty and love of country, despite social problems such as violence and verbal abuse. He talks about his grandparents' alcoholism and abuse, his unstable mother's drug history and failed relationships. Vance's grandparents eventually reconciled and became his de facto guardians. He was pushed by his strict but loving grandmother and eventually managed to leave Vance Middleton and attend Ohio State University and Yale Law School.

Along with his personal history, Vance raises questions such as the responsibility of his family and his people for his misfortune. Vance blames hillbilly culture and its promotion of social decay. Relatively speaking, he believes that economic uncertainty plays a lesser role. Vance regularly draws on personal experience to support his argument. As a grocery store cashier, she watched welfare recipients talk on cell phones, even though Vance, who worked, couldn't afford one. His distaste for those who profited from bad behavior during the struggle, especially when combined with the values of personal responsibility and tough love, is presented as a microcosm of the cause of Appalachia's overall political shift from strong Democratic to strong Republican affiliation. Similarly, he shared stories intended to show a lack of work ethic, including the story of a co-worker who quit after expressing distaste for his work hours and posted about the "Obama economy" on social media.

RESULTS

In memoirs, the narrator and the author are always the same. Memories are also always told in the first person (with I/My language). This increases the subjectivity of memoirs, because although they are based on real events, the way these events are presented to the reader is synonymous with the way the author experienced the event.

This feature also ensures that each memoir is unique in the sense of reflecting its author's narrative style, language and speech style, and most importantly, his thoughts.

The basic agreement between the author and the reader is that the author presents his version of what he believes to be true. Although memoirs contain the facts of an event, they are subjective in the sense that they retell the event based on how the author

experienced it and how the author remembers it. The author is in no way responsible for retelling the story from the perspective of how others may have experienced it. It also involves taking into account the weaknesses of human memory - not every detail can be actually written down and remembered, especially when it comes to dialogues. However, the author should avoid fictional encounters and capture the truth as much as possible.

CONCLUSION

Memoirs are never published as independent works. Usually, they are published in a series of anecdotes connected by a common theme. For example, "A Memoir of a Family and Culture in Crisis" by James David Vance. This can take the form of consistency in installation, meaning that all memories are installed at the same time or in the same place. In the author's view, memories can be combined with their content and lessons.

Memoir writers have the ability to convey what they've learned from their experiences and help readers gain insight into the lives of others and how those lessons apply to their own.

Memoir - main conclusions:

Memoirs are a collection of memories that the author intended to capture events from his life.

The style and language used in writing a memoir are as important as the subject matter. It's not just what you say, but how you say it

- Features of this memoir:
- First person narrative voice
- Truth
- Subject
- Identity and similarity
- An emotional journey

In addition to presenting a story, a memoir reflects on the content of the story.

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